

CURRENT STATE AND EXISTING PROBLEMS OF TECHNOLOGICAL EDUCATION

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Annotation:

This article analyzes the current state of technological education, its stages of development, and its role in the education system. It also examines the main problems encountered in organizing technological education, including the недостатacy of material and technical resources, lack of modern equipment and resources, the qualification level of teachers, and the mismatch of curricula with modern requirements. The article substantiates ways to eliminate these problems, as well as the need to introduce innovative approaches and advanced foreign experience. At the same time, special attention is given to developing students' practical skills and guiding them toward vocational careers through technological education.

Keywords:

technological education, education system, innovation, practical skills, vocational training, modern technologies, curriculum, material and technical base, pedagogical approach, problems and solutions.

Introduction

Today, technological education is considered one of the important areas of the education system. This is because technology and technical fields are rapidly developing in modern society. Therefore, it is important to provide students not only with theoretical knowledge but also with practical skills. Through technological education, students learn various vocational skills and prepare for their future careers. At the same time, there are still some problems in the system of technological education that negatively affect the quality of education. This article discusses the current state and existing problems of technological education.

Main Part

Currently, technological education is taught as a separate subject in schools and higher educational institutions. During lessons, students are taught how to work with tools, create simple technical objects, and design projects. This helps to develop students' creativity and independent thinking. However, in practice, there are some shortcomings. One of the main problems is the lack of sufficient material and technical resources. In many educational institutions, modern equipment is either lacking or outdated, which reduces the effectiveness of lessons.

Another problem is the insufficient qualification of teachers in modern technologies. In some cases, teachers face difficulties in applying new methods. In addition, the curriculum does not always meet modern requirements. To solve these problems, it is necessary to equip

educational institutions with modern technology, improve teachers' qualifications, and introduce new teaching methods.

Conclusion

In conclusion, technological education is very important today. It plays a significant role in developing students' practical skills. At the same time, by solving existing problems, the quality of education can be improved. If sufficient attention is paid to technological education, I believe that qualified and competitive specialists will be trained in the future.

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